

Role of teacher learning agility: an empirical study for islamic educational success in Indonesia

Susanto¹, Nur Afif², Apri Wardana Ritonga³, Ayu Desrani⁴, Akhmad Shunhaji¹, Ahmadi⁵

¹Department of Islamic Education Management, Postgraduate University PTIQ Jakarta, Jakarta, Indonesia

²Department of Early Childhood Islamic Education, University PTIQ, Jakarta, Indonesia

³Department of Arabic Language Education, As-Syifa College of Qur'anic Science, Subang, Indonesia

⁴Department of Arabic Language Education, Islamic Institute of Musdaryah Cimahi, Cimahi, Indonesia

⁵Department of Islamic Education Management, State Islamic Institute Ponorogo, Ponorogo, Indonesia

Article Info

Article history:

Received Aug 23, 2023

Revised Feb 13, 2024

Accepted Feb 28, 2024

Keywords:

Educational success

Islamic education

Learning agility

Learning transformation

Self-competence

ABSTRACT

This research aims to analyze the role of teacher learning agility in supporting the success of Islamic education in Indonesia. Researchers used a survey method distributed via a Google Form questionnaire. The population of this study were elementary, middle school, high school, bachelor's and master's level teachers, and a sample of 517 people was obtained, taken using random sampling techniques with the classification of 150 elementary school teachers, 135 middle school teachers, 148 high school teachers, 85 undergraduate lecturers, and 53 master level lecturers. The data were analyzed descriptively and measured using the analysis of variance (ANOVA) test assisted by the SPSS 22 program. The results of the research show that outstanding educators in Indonesia have high learning agility at work. More than 50% of respondents respond to current developments and apply learning agility in the workplace. Based on job classification, lecturers have higher learning agility with an overall average of above 4.20. Meanwhile, based on gender, women are superior to men in its application. Educators with learning agility display maximum work performance, are able to draw lessons from work experience, adapt to change with full awareness and enthusiasm for learning to improve their skills, knowledge and competence.

This is an open access article under the [CC BY-SA](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/4.0/) license.

Corresponding Author:

Susanto

Department of Islamic Education Management, Postgraduate University PTIQ Jakarta

St. Lebak Bulus Raya No. 2 Cilandak, Jakarta Selatan, Jakarta-12440, Indonesia

Email: susanto@ptiq.ac.id

1. INTRODUCTION

Meuse [1] says that learning agility is defined as the determination and capacity to take lessons from what has been experienced before to be implemented through additional challenges in the role of the next responsibility. In supporting the improvement of teacher performance, competency, and achievement, it is necessary to have learning agility. Learning agility is related to every individual such as a teacher who has the adaptive capacity and willingness to deal with all uncertain situations in the future [2], [3]. For a teacher, Learning agility is one solution for transforming oneself into a meaningful person through the experiences one encounters are packaged into meaningful knowledge. Teachers who have learning agility always bring innovation [4] and are able to survive amidst global developments [5].

In education, according to Hallenbeck and Santana [6] learning agility is the main factor that distinguishes a teacher from others in extracting various lessons learned from experience and then applying

them. The dimensions of learning agility include people agility, mental agility, change agility, and result agility [7]. People agility teachers tend to be open-minded and comfortable with diversity and different opinions [8]. Result of agility teachers tend to have high enthusiasm in completing tasks and can complete tasks well even though there are obstacles [9]. Furthermore, teachers with mental agility tend to have a high curiosity about something and can find solutions to problems that tend to be difficult [10]. Then, teachers with change agility tend to like challenges at work and easily accept new challenges.

Meuse [1] concluded that the five dimensions of learning agility are the skills possessed by learning agility which is one of the criteria used to measure teacher success in education. This learning agility ability can make a teacher become someone who is tough and has no fear of dealing with change [11], [12]. Changes in the world of education occur very quickly, transitions, and developments are things that need attention, this is because individuals are faced with unknown circumstances which are routine and which leadership is not suitable for dealing with change [10]. López-Alcarria *et al.* [13] argues that creating agile teachers to deal with change, collaboration in advancing education, carrying out roles and functions as educators, and sharing knowledge and information are challenges that are often faced today.

Learning agility is related to the teacher's experience of taking lessons in every action. Experience is the most valuable lesson [14]. Meuse [15] argues that teachers who can learn from previous experiences and apply them in new situations and are interested in new challenges, proactively seek feedback from others to grow and develop [16], introspect themselves and evaluate experiences and draw conclusions are teachers with high learning agility [17]. The role of agile teachers is vital because teachers who have high agility learning skills know the contributions and actions they will take and actively contribute to their educational institutions.

Currently, researchers and academics are paying attention to the issue of teacher learning agility. The researcher noted a review of previous research related to the following topics as carried out by [5] revealed that teacher learning agility is often successful in producing graduates with complex problem-solving skills involving 5 learning cycles: individual discovery, disciplinary collaboration, interdisciplinary collaboration, expert evaluation, and reflection. The results of the study [18] show that the agility of outstanding teachers displays maximum performance, learn from previous experiences, adapt to changes, and continue to learn to improve skills, knowledge, and self-competence. The results of the study [19] explain that learning agility can also be influenced by factors of age, work experience, position level, and position in the office.

However, in the context of Islamic education in Indonesia, similar research is still scarce. Even though it has been done before, the object of study is centered on employees with a corporate work base, not educational institutions. Meanwhile, educational success is largely determined by the role of agile teachers. Therefore, this research aims to analyze the role of learning agility teachers in the success of Islamic education in Indonesia. Through this research, researchers hope to get a fundamental approach for teachers to improve learning agility in an era of massive change and development. In this way, the study of teacher learning agility contributes to the modernity and transformation of education in Indonesia.

2. METHOD

2.1. Research design

This research uses a quantitative approach with a survey method. This method is used to solve actual large-scale issue problems with very large populations, large sample sizes are required. The purpose of this research itself is to use a survey method to see the ability to be able to learn new things quickly and accurately to adapt to the new era. Where the ability and speed of learning are very important, especially on the job.

2.2. Data collection and participant

Survey data is collected using a Google Form which is distributed to respondents. The sample selection technique used purposive random sampling with the respondent category coming from 517 teaching staff with a classification of 150 elementary school level teachers, 135 junior high school level teachers, 148 senior high school level teachers, 85 people as lecturers for the bachelor level, and there were 53 lecturers for the master level. All respondents came from Islamic educational institutions spread across several provinces, namely the provinces of South Sumatra, North Sumatra, West Sumatra, West Java, Central Java, and East Java. Overall, the respondents are described as Figure 1.

2.3. Instrument

The distribution of survey instruments was tested for validity and reliability by an expert to determine the quality of the instrument and the level of confidence in the data being distributed. Overall, this instrument is in the form of a questionnaire to find primary data, which is distributed using Google Forms to

see the learning agility of respondents. This study focuses on learning agility variables, namely people agility, change agility, mental agility, and agility results. The instrument questions are categorized according to the research variables, with as many as 20 questions for each variable indicator. The instrument that has been created was tested for validity and reliability using SPSS 22. And it was found that a total of 20 question items were declared valid and reliable. The basis for this decision is because the overall value of the calculated r is greater than the r table, where the value of the r table with a sample of 517 is only 0.088 and the calculated value is >0.088 , so all items are declared valid. The reliability value can be determined from the results of Cronbach's alpha, the condition of which is that if the value is greater than 0.60, it is declared reliable, and the reliable value obtained is 0.77.

2.4. Data analysis

Before carrying out hypothesis testing, researchers carry out normality and homogeneity tests to see that the data to be tested is normally distributed and homogeneous so that final testing can be continued. All data was analyzed through tabulation using a Likert scale by changing the respondent's answer choices into scores of 1, 2, 3, 4, and 5 according to the instrument score table. The total score is then determined, followed by calculating the average. All data was processed and analyzed using statistics with the analysis of variance (ANOVA) test to see differences between sample groups in learning agility. Data analysis was assisted by the SPSS 22 program.

Figure 1. Participant information

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Result

Before the authors perform the statistical and ANOVA tests, the researchers first perform the normality and homogeneity tests. The normality test is a procedure used to determine whether the data comes from a normal-distributed population or is within the normal range. The normality test used in this study is Kolmogorov-Smirnov and Shapiro-Wilk. The basis of decision-making for the normality test is that when the value of significance or probability is >0.05 , then the data concluded is normally distributed, whereas homogeneity testing is a statistical test procedure intended to show that two or more groups of sample data originate from populations that have the same variance. In other words, homogeneity means that the data sets studied have the same characteristics. The basis for taking the adjustment for the homogeneity test is that when the value of the lavane statistic >0.05 , then the data is homogenous or has the same characters. The normality and homogeneity test results see Table 1.

The normality test in Table 1 above shows that elementary school has the smallest significance, namely 0.19. Junior high school and senior high school show the same significance of 0.200. And bachelor shows a significance of 0.092. While postgraduate 0.230. From these overall results, it can be concluded that the significance of all variables is >0.05 , which means that the data distribution is normal. Then the data taken stated that there are no deviations and that is feasible for the ANOVA test.

The variance homogeneity test in Table 2 above aims to test whether the ANOVA assumptions apply, namely whether the five sample groups have the same variance. The variance uniformity test shows that the probability or significance of all samples is 0.085, which means $\text{significance}=0.085 > 0.05$, so according to the test criteria it can be concluded that the null hypothesis (H_0) is accepted, which means that the assumption that the four population variants are the same (homogeneous) is acceptable. Learning agility based on responses from the teaching respondent category see Table 3.

Based on the Table 3 above, it is known that each of the first variables is community agility at the elementary and undergraduate levels, they obtained the same average, namely 4.09, with the lowest average score, namely at the senior high school level, 4.07 and the highest was obtained by samples from postgraduate, namely 4.20. means that the postgraduate sample gets the highest score applying people agility where people who achieve high scores for people agility are constructive towards others and open to people who have different backgrounds and opinions, and have good communication, interpersonal and leadership skills in carrying out learning.

Tabel 1. Test of normality

Variabels		Kolmogorov-smirnov ^a			Shapiro-wilk		
		statistic	df	Sig.	Statistic	df	Sig.
Learning Agility	Elementary School	.140	40	.019	.720	40	.064
	Junior High School	.154	40	0.200	.749	40	.112
	Senior High School	.150	40	0.200	.784	40	.124
	Bachelor	.172	40	0.092	.812	40	.106
	Postgraduate	.189	40	0.230	.921	40	.243

Tabel 2. Test of homogeneity of variances

Levene statistic	df1	df2	Sig.
.298	2	47	.085

Table 3. Learning agility based on variables and job categories

Varibales	Groups	N	M	SD	t	df	p
People Agility	Elementary School	150	4.09	43	2.180	380	.001
	Junior High School	135	4.11	50			
	Senior High School	148	4.07	45			
	Bachelor	85	4.09	54			
	Postgraduate	53	4.20	48			
Change Agility	Elementary School	150	4.04	40	2.173	380	.004
	Junior High School	135	4.24	51			
	Senior High School	148	4.11	57			
	Bachelor	85	4.23	44			
	Postgraduate	53	4.27	40			
Mental Agility	Elementary School	150	4.02	43	1.950	380	.008
	Junior High School	135	4.23	45			
	Senior High School	148	4.10	55			
	Bachelor	85	4.17	58			
	Postgraduate	53	4.27	43			
Results Agility	Elementary School	150	4.13	46	1.763	380	.012
	Junior High School	135	4.06	50			
	Senior High School	148	4.12	41			
	Bachelor	85	4.19	44			
	Postgraduate	53	4.28	40			

If we look again at the table above on the aspects of change agility, mental agility, and agility results it is also obtained that the greatest value is at the postgraduate education level N=53 the lecturers studied from various fields of study, namely change agility and mental agility get an average of 4.27, while the agility results are 4.28. This means that the postgraduate sample is more dominating and applies more learning agility. And significantly the sample at the postgraduate level has a strong desire to develop their abilities and competencies by continuing to learn new things related to work and are very ready to face challenges at work. This is also influenced by long experiences in education.

However, if you look again in detail, apart from the postgraduate sample, you get different values for each variable. The elementary school sample still holds the lowest average score in dealing with change agility than the other samples, which is 4.04. It also has the lowest average in the mental agility aspect, namely 4.02. whereas in the junior high school sample, the value number 2 after postgraduate was obtained, namely change agility of 4.24, mental agility of 4.23, and the lowest agility results of 4.06.

While the P value is very significant that the people's agility of all samples is in their educational status, namely (0.001 $p < 0.05$) where the sample significantly shows their ability to become people agility. Change agility (0.004 $p < 0.05$), mental agility (0.008 $p < 0.05$), and agility results (0.012 $p < 0.05$) in other words significantly the variables of this learning agility are significantly related to one another or in other words after the four variants are proven to be the same, then the ANOVA test is carried out to test whether the four samples have the same average. The ANOVA test shows a probability or significance value of less

than 0.05. This means the significance is less than 0.05 than H_a accepted, which means that there is an average difference between the five sample groups tested. Learning agility based on gender category see Table 4.

In Table 4 above it is very clear that the female sample with a total of 356 dominates the learning agility variables. In the variable people's agility female has an average of 4.28 with a value (0.003 $p < 0.05$) meaning this female gender is more dominant against adaptability in dealing with many human characters. Because, the faster you adapt to other people's characters, the easier it will be for you to work together in doing work. Aspects of change agility 4.23 and (0.007 $p < 0.05$) where these women have an open mindset (growth mindset), where this mindset tends to make a person more open and like various types of changes that occur in their environment and life, mental agility 4.15 and (0.011 $p < 0.05$) where people who have mental agility can think, learn, and absorb information quickly, and agility results of 4.26 with a significance (0.015 $p < 0.05$) meaning people who have results agility ability he prioritizes results-oriented work. while the male sample has an average of 4.12 people agility variables, 4.09 change agility, 4.14 mental agility, and 4.04 results agility. probability or overall significance < 0.05 this means a significance smaller than 0.05 then H_a accepted, which means that there is an average difference between the two groups. The result of this statement is that the female dominates in various variables, of course, this is also influenced by the female sample being larger than the male sample. What can be seen is the significance of the variables so that the needs of the variables are related to one another.

Table 4. Learning agility based on variables and gender

Variables	Groups	N	M	SD	t	df	p
People Agility	Male	215	4.12	48	2.450	380	.003
	Female	356	4.28	47			
Change Agility	Male	215	4.09	54	2.238	380	.007
	Female	356	4.23	49			
Mental Agility	Male	215	4.14	57	1.887	380	.011
	Female	356	4.15	52			
Result Agility	Male	215	4.04	41	1.743	380	.015
	Female	356	4.26	46			

3.2. Discussion

In this study, we investigate whether teacher learning agility can improve the quality of Islamic education in Indonesia. According to estimates resulting from quantitative data processing, it was found that the learning agility of teachers has a beneficial influence on the quality of Islamic education in Indonesia. In addition, the learning agility of educational staff also has a significant effect on improving the quality of Islamic education institutions which refer to learning agility indicators, namely people agility, change agility, mental agility, and result agility. In principle, the success of teacher learning agility is closely related to the principal's leadership management process to increase the capacity of superior human resources in Islamic education institutions.

Education is the main choice for creating and improving the competence of Indonesia's human resources. Many studies have proven that education has positive implications for a person's thinking skills through the transformation of educational models that are in line with current developments [20], [21]. Susanto's *et al.* [22] research results state that educational transformation is intended to provide changes in contemporary educational styles that are adaptive to situations and conditions. The author believes that changing the national curriculum to the "Independent Curriculum" style in schools and universities is seen as the first step in producing graduates who are tough, agile, competitive, independent, and have a leadership spirit for the nation's future. Islamic educational institutions as places for religious learning must, of course, be alert and responsive [23]. This alert and responsive attitude usually begins with the teacher's efforts to design learning materials and then teach them using a style, method, and language that are close to the students.

Different research results reveal that learning transformation can be achieved by using learning agility skills. This statement correlates with [2] and is emphasized by [24], which reveals that learning agility skills can occur in someone who has a strong desire to change from one condition to adapt to a new situation. Muduli's research states that learning agility is a core competency for a teacher with which they can see solutions to various problems found in learning, especially in efforts to equip students with good knowledge and skills [25]. Lee and Song's [3] research findings support previous research that teacher learning agility requires concrete and structured steps to face changes in education due to massive developments in technology. Especially in Islamic education, which requires a courageous attitude to dismantle static and underestimated thoughts to utilize technology as an instrument for growth and development in the global arena [13].

Islamic education is currently very responsive to changing times by continuing to increase teacher capacity in the learning process through learning agility. This statement is proven by the results of the research above which show the responses of the respondents in implementing the variables which are indicators of learning agility. Santoso and Yuzarion [18], learning agility indicators must reflect the following attitudes: i) People agility: they are individuals who understand themselves well, learn from experience, are calm and professional, and build constructive relationships with different people [19]; ii) Result agility: they are trusted individuals who can achieve superior results in difficult circumstances and support others to achieve high [26]; iii) Mental agility: it identifies individuals who are comfortable with complex events, carefully examining issues and establishing relationships between different elements [19]; iv) Change agility: expressing people who are curious, broad-minded, and willing to participate in activities that can gain experience and develop skills [18].

Researchers also surveyed respondents' efforts when positioning themselves as teachers in Islamic educational institutions. Based on the diagram above, as much as 80% of respondents can take on challenges. There 53% of respondents claim to have the ability to learn from experience and apply new knowledge. As many as 80% of respondents said they respect something certain and unambiguous. Meanwhile, 20% of the respondents did not question being in ambiguity. Furthermore, 63% of respondents said they were flexible people, easily adaptable to new environments and changes in education policies. On another indicator, 67% of respondents said they were open-minded and like to learn from experts. At its peak, there were 73% of respondents who were able to diagnose student learning problems and find solutions to overcome them. The results of this research correlate with the paper Kim *et al.* [10] the teacher has a comprehensive understanding of the learning situation in the classroom to bring students learning comfort that can support maximum learning outcomes.

Today, learning success is no longer borne by subject teachers. All education stakeholders have a vital role to achieve this goal. Even, Ritonga *et al.* [27] said that today students can access learning independently anytime and anywhere without having to wait for direct instructions from the teacher. Agility learning skills measure whether a person has the potential to quickly familiarize himself with new issues in the context of Islamic education [23]. The issue of Islamic education is seen as relevant to today's uncertain situation where students' moral shifts are increasingly being eroded. Tripathi and Sankaran [28] reveals people with good learning agility skills can quickly understand and familiarize themselves with problems in all kinds of new situations. Learning agility scanning makes it easier for you as a school management team to identify teachers who can maintain the strength and dynamism of your organization into the future. Previous research has found that learning agility contributes to positive change in Islamic educational institutions.

In the concept of Islamic education, teachers are positioned as noble people, because of their role in educating humans, so many rules make teachers special in front of society [29]. However, our research sees that Islam also requires that everyone who becomes a teacher must be a good and devout human being and be open to all developments of the times for the sake of the progress of Islamic education. This is commensurate with the paper [30] which explains the teacher's attitude as a role model in his daily life, carrying out actions in accordance with applicable ethics and rules, such as religious principles, state regulations, social regulations, and so on. Meanwhile, the meaning of a teacher must be good, that is, every member of his body always moves towards goodness, not violating the rules that have been mentioned. This is part of the signaling foundation for teachers to continue learning and upgrading their capacities through learning agility so that teachers in Islamic education are professional, broad-minded, open-minded, and adaptive to change.

Of course, it becomes a heavy burden for teachers to be human beings who are always demanded to be right and good, while teachers themselves are ordinary people who make mistakes and forget. Susanto *et al.* [23] strengthens the principle of the teacher as a person who is always a role model with Islamic guidance through maximum efforts to carry out lifelong learning. The term "long life education" is an Islamic jargon that guides people to learn from various life problems and environmental complexities throughout their lives so they are not trapped with shallow and limited knowledge amid vast knowledge. The essence of learning is only the realization of students who are intelligent and have noble character [31]. This means that teachers are required to be able to practice Islamic values to guide students to become quality human beings [32]. The meaning of quality in question is, students who have strong reasoning power, have a strong enthusiasm for life, and at the same time have commendable attitudes and behavior, so that they can survive with various challenges of the times.

The authors found that knowledge of the agile paradigm is an initial stage in facing changing times before individuals engage in agile practices. At the agile mindset stage it is more about how a student responds to change. This is different from [13] findings which require students to have agile abilities to be adaptive to global change. This finding has similarities with [33] who demands that Islamic education be transformed according to the demands of the times so that it is not confined by narrow thinking to a broad understanding of Islam. Teachers who have an agile mindset are teachers who always have creative ideas in their heads that will be implemented in their learning [34]. Agility applied in learning innovation is a very important trigger for making changes in learning.

This study illustrates an agile mindset teacher, such as being able to turn a study room into a wilderness where various types of plants with their uniqueness and specifications live. Making study spaces not only agricultural land or plantations planted with one or two types of plants but how can learning spaces become wilderness in which there are various kinds of potential for students and get the same right to grow and develop. Creating an agile learning atmosphere with the development of students' thinking power has been the goal of Islamic education institutions for a long time with consideration of teacher learning agility incorporating dimensions of creative thinking and being open-minded to the opportunities as well as challenges of future Islamic education.

4. CONCLUSION

This research has implications for the process of increasing the creativity of teachers in Islamic education institutions by incorporating aspects of learning agility such as people agility, change agility, mental agility, and result agility so that learning outcomes in schools have a positive impact on students, and at the same time there is an increase the quality of the Islamic educational institutions. Islamic education today is experiencing very rapid changes. This is marked by the many Islamic educational institutions that respond to developments and advances in learning technology which are indicators of modern and independent education. The results of this study encourage teachers to quickly respond to learning agility skills to help prepare a generation that is resilient, agile, and adaptive to subsequent changes.

The findings of this research reveal that in-depth and comprehensive knowledge about learning agility is the initial stage for every student in facing changing times before they engage in agile practices. In the respondent category, it turns out that there is a relationship between each variable, this is obtained from the ANOVA test value proving a probability and significance value of less than 0.05. This means the significance is less than 0.05 then H_0 accepted, which means that there is an average difference between the five sample groups tested. Whereas in the aspect of the gender category itself, the overall probability or significance is <0.05 , which means a small significance of 0.05, so H_0 accepted, which means there is an average difference between the two groups. This difference is only limited to how respondents apply learning agility in the learning process. However, there is no fundamental difference to humiliate or discriminate against a group.

On other indicators, teaching experience and the experience of a teacher also influence responding to changes in education policy. Teachers with high-flying hours are quicker and easier to diagnose learning problems and find the best solutions according to the needs of the times. Likewise, those who are in a technological environment and get complete facilities will continue to improve their skills in responding to learning agility. Researchers hope that this learning agility study can be responded to and applied properly to the Islamic educational institutions studied and can be extended to educational institutions in general, both formal and non-formal. This research is limited to the position of learning agility teachers for the success of Islamic education in Indonesia, so there is still a lot of space that needs to be developed to complement and correct the deficiencies of this text, for example, the role of learning agility teachers for the successful implementation of the independent learning curriculum in Indonesia by involving a more global sample supported by a more global approach. and a more comprehensive method.

REFERENCES

- [1] K. P. De Meuse, "Learning Agility: Its Evolution as a Psychological Construct and its Empirical Relationship to Leader Success.," *Consult. Psychol. J. Pract. Res.*, vol. 69, no. 4, pp. 267–295, Dec. 2017, doi: 10.1037/cpb0000100.
- [2] H. Ab Jalil, I. A. Ismail, A. M. Ma'rof, C. L. Lim, N. Hassan, and N. R. Che Nawi, "Predicting Learners' Agility and Readiness for Future Learning Ecosystem," *Educ. Sci.*, vol. 12, no. 10, 2022, doi: 10.3390/educsci12100680.
- [3] J. Lee and J. H. Song, "Developing a Conceptual Integrated Model for the Employee's Learning Agility," *Perform. Improv. Q.*, vol. 34, no. 4, pp. 367–394, Jan. 2022, doi: 10.1002/piq.21352.
- [4] H. Collins, "Future Work Skills Response: A Teaching Transformation Using Agility and Evidence," *Stud. Technol. Enhanc. Learn.*, vol. 3, no. 2, Jun. 2023, doi: 10.21428/8c225f6e.9b1a2982.
- [5] C. Azionya and A. Oksitycz, "A Teaching Model to Promote Learning Agility in a University Course," *Indep. J. Teach. Learn.*, vol. 14, no. 1, pp. 6–18, 2019, doi: 10.10520/EJC-168565bdf9.
- [6] G. Hallenbeck and L. Santana, "Great Leaders Are Great Learners: How to Develop Learning-Agile High Potentials Contents," *Cent. Creat. Leadersh.*, pp. 1–13, 2019.
- [7] K. P. De Meuse, "Learning Agility: Could it Become the g-Factor of Leadership?," *Consult. Psychol. J.*, vol. 74, no. 3, pp. 215–236, Sep. 2022, doi: 10.1037/cpb0000216.
- [8] P. Caligiuri, "Build Your Cultural Agility: The Nine Competencies of Successful Global Professionals," *Kogan Page Publishers*, 2021.
- [9] Z. K. Ellala *et al.*, "The Role of Students' Agility and Students' Interest in the Linguistic Intelligence among Gifted Students in Higher Education Institutions," *Eurasian J. Educ. Res.*, vol. 2022, no. 100, pp. 206–221, 2022, doi: 10.14689/ejer.2022.100.014.
- [10] H. J. Kim, A. J. Hong, and H. D. Song, "The Relationships of Family, Perceived Digital Competence and Attitude, and Learning Agility in Sustainable Student Engagement in Higher Education," *Sustain.*, vol. 10, no. 12, 2018, doi: 10.3390/su10124635.
- [11] M. K. Omar and A. H. M. Rahman, "Learning Agility, Emotional Intelligence and Change Adoption Among Teachers in

- Terengganu, Malaysia,” in *AIP Conf. Proc.*, 2023, p. 060007, doi: 10.1063/5.0115641.
- [12] A. Tripathi, R. Srivastava, and R. Sankaran, “Role of Learning Agility and Learning Culture on Turnover Intention: An Empirical Study,” *Ind. Commer. Train.*, vol. 52, no. 2, pp. 105–120, May 2020, doi: 10.1108/ICT-11-2019-0099.
- [13] A. López-Alcarria, A. Olivares-Vicente, and F. Poza-Vilches, “A Systematic Review of the Use of Agile Methodologies in Education to Foster Sustainability Competencies,” *Sustain.*, vol. 11, no. 10, pp. 1–29, 2019, doi: 10.3390/su11102915.
- [14] A. Forsyth and R. Peiser, “Lessons from Planned Resettlement and New Town Experiences for Avoiding Climate Sprawl,” *Landsc. Urban Plan.*, vol. 205, p. 103957, Jan. 2021, doi: 10.1016/j.landurbplan.2020.103957.
- [15] K. P. De Meuse, G. Dai, and G. S. Hallenbeck, “Learning Agility: A Construct whose Time has Come,” *Educational Publishing Foundation*, vol. 62, no. 2., 2010.
- [16] M. Abdelaziz, “Learning Agility and Language Learning,” *Seminar*, vol. 1, no. 1, pp. 1–21, 2023, doi: 10.21608/smnar.1999.300893.
- [17] K. Setemen, I. G. Sudirtha, and I. W. Widiana, “The Effectiveness of Study, Explore, Implement, Evaluate E-Learning Model Based on Project-Based Learning on the Students Conceptual Understanding and Learning Agility,” *J. Technol. Sci. Educ.*, vol. 13, no. 3, pp. 583–596, 2023, doi: 10.3926/jotse.1624.
- [18] A. M. Santoso and Y. Yuzarion, “Analysis of Learning Agility in the Performance of Achievement Teachers in Yogyakarta,” *Pedagog. J. Pendidik.*, vol. 8, no. 1, pp. 77–122, 2021, doi: 10.33650/pjp.v8i1.2126.
- [19] M. Özgenel and Ş. Yazici, “Learning Agility of School Administrators: An Empirical Investigation,” *Int. J. Progress. Educ.*, vol. 17, no. 1, pp. 247–261, 2021, doi: 10.29329/ijpe.2021.329.16.
- [20] F. Castellacci and V. Tveito, “Internet Use and well-being: A Survey and a Theoretical Framework,” *Res. Policy*, vol. 47, no. 1, pp. 308–325, Feb. 2018, doi: 10.1016/j.respol.2017.11.007.
- [21] L. I. González-Pérez and M. S. Ramírez-Montoya, “Components of Education 4.0 in 21st Century Skills Frameworks: Systematic Review,” *Sustainability*, vol. 14, no. 3, p. 1493, Jan. 2022, doi: 10.3390/su14031493.
- [22] S. Susanto, E. Muafiah, A. Desrani, A. W. Ritonga, and A. R. Hakim, “Trends of Educational Technology (EdTech): Students’ Perceptions of Technology to Improve the Quality of Islamic Higher Education in Indonesia,” *Int. J. Learn. Teach. Educ. Res.*, vol. 21, no. 6, pp. 226–246, 2022, doi: 10.26803/ijlter.21.6.14.
- [23] S. Susanto, A. W. Ritonga, and A. Desrani, “Innovation Management Plan for Quality Improvement of Madrasah in Covid-19 Situation,” *Aspir. J. Masal. Sos.*, vol. 13, no. 1, pp. 117–133, 2022, doi: 10.46807/aspirasi.v13i1.3001.
- [24] M. K. H. Petermann and H. Zacher, “Agility in the Workplace: Conceptual Aanalysis, Contributing Factors, and Practical Examples,” *Ind. Organ. Psychol.*, vol. 13, no. 4, pp. 599–609, Dec. 2020, doi: 10.1017/iop.2020.106.
- [25] L. Muduli, D. P. Mishra, and P. K. Jana, “Application of Wireless Sensor Network for Environmental Monitoring in Underground Coal Mines: A Systematic Review,” *J. Netw. Comput. Appl.*, vol. 106, pp. 48–67, Mar. 2018, doi: 10.1016/j.jnca.2017.12.022.
- [26] Y. Doz, “Fostering Strategic Agility: How Individual Executives and Human Resource Practices Contribute,” *Hum. Resour. Manag. Rev.*, vol. 30, no. 1, p. 100693, Mar. 2020, doi: 10.1016/j.hrmr.2019.100693.
- [27] M. Ritonga, R. Hakim, T. Nurdianto, and A. W. Ritonga, “Learning for Early Childhood Using the IcanDO Platform: Breakthroughs for Golden Age Education in Arabic Learning,” *Educ. Inf. Technol.*, no. 0123456789, 2023, doi: 10.1007/s10639-022-11575-7.
- [28] A. Tripathi and R. Sankaran, “Improving the Retention of Employees Through Organisational Learning Culture: The Mediating Role of Learning Agility and the Moderating Role of Gender,” *Int. J. Knowl. Learn.*, vol. 14, no. 4, p. 301, 2021, doi: 10.1504/IJKL.2021.118553.
- [29] T. Asif, O. Guangming, M. A. Haider, J. Colomer, S. Kayani, and N. ul Amin, “Moral Education for Sustainable Development: Comparison of University Teachers’ Perceptions in China and Pakistan,” *Sustain.*, vol. 12, no. 7, 2020, doi: 10.3390/su12073014.
- [30] L. Măță, O. Clipa, and K. Tzafilkou, “The Development and Validation of a Scale to Measure University Teachers’ Attitude towards Ethical Use of Information Technology for a Sustainable Education,” *Sustain.*, vol. 12, no. 15, 2020, doi: 10.3390/SU12156268.
- [31] Susanto, A. W. Ritonga, and A. Desrani, “The Challenge of The Integrated Character Education Paradigm with 21st-Century Skills During The Covid-19 Pandemic,” *Cendekia J. Kependidikan dan Kemasyarakatan*, vol. 20, no. 1, pp. 85–104, 2022, doi: 10.21154/cendekia.v1i1.3816.
- [32] Susanto, A. Desrani, A. W. Ritonga, Ramli, M. Lubis, and Nurdin, “Learning by Doing: A Teaching Paradigm for Active Learning in Islamic High School,” *J. Educ. e-Learning Res.*, vol. 10, no. 4, pp. 793–799, 2023, doi: 10.20448/jeelr.v10i4.5224.
- [33] A. Sabic-El-Rayess, “Epistemological Shifts in Knowledge and Education in Islam: A New Perspective on the Emergence of Radicalization Amongst Muslims,” *Int. J. Educ. Dev.*, vol. 73, p. 102148, Mar. 2020, doi: 10.1016/j.ijedudev.2019.102148.
- [34] D. Parsons and K. MacCallum, “Agile and Lean Concepts for Teaching and Learning: Bringing Methodologies from Industry to the Classroom,” *Singapore: Springer Singapore*, 2019.

BIOGRAPHIES OF AUTHORS

Susanto is an associate professor of Islamic education. Currently he is a postgraduate lecturer at University of PTIQ Jakarta. During his studies, Susanto was a smart person. This was proven when he became the best graduate during undergraduate and postgraduate graduations. In fact, he also completed his doctoral education when he was 38 years old. Not only that, Susanto is recorded as having an excellent career as a lecturer. He was also a Consultant Team for Gender Mainstreaming and Child Protection, Ministry of Women’s Empowerment and Child Protection. Until finally he was elected chairman of the KPAI for the 2017-2022 term. Currently he is pursuing research in accordance with his field of Islamic education and is focused on becoming an outstanding academic. He can be contacted at email: susanto@ptiq.ac.id.

Nur Afif is a lecturer in the Department of Early Childhood Islamic Education. He graduated from doctoral level from the campus where he served as a lecturer. As a lecturer, he actively carries out activities to develop the Tri Dharma of Higher Education such as teaching, research and community service. Apart from that, he is also often involved as a speaker in national seminars on Islamic education which is very relevant to the science he is pursuing. He has successfully published many articles and books as part of the development of science and technology. Among the popular texts he wrote are “Tafsir Tarbawi: Educational Messages in the Al-Quran”, problem-based learning perspective of the Al-Qur’an”, and many more. He can be contacted at email: nurafif@ptiq.ac.id.

Apri Wardana Ritonga is a lecturer at As-Syifa Al-Qur’an High School in Subang. He completed his undergraduate and postgraduate studies from the Arabic language education department and is currently pursuing his doctoral degree in the same department using an LPDP scholarship. He devotes a lot of his ideas and ideas through research in various fields of Arabic language education, Islamic Studies, Social, and character education. All of these papers have been published in reputable journals and even some of their writings have been published in reputable international journals indexed Scopus Q1 SJR 1.25. He is committed to serving the country as an academic until one day he is awarded a professorship. He can be contacted at email: apriwardanaritonga@stiq.assyifa.ac.id.

Ayu Desrani she graduated from the 2018 Bachelor of Education in Department of Arabic Language Education at the Raden Fatah State Islamic University Palembang and completed the 2020 Masters level in Department of Arabic Language Education at the State Islamic University of Maulana Malik Ibrahim Malang. She has internship experience as an Arabic teacher at MIN 1 Palembang and MAN 1 Malang. And now she is a permanent lecturer at STAI Musdariyah Cimahi. She teaches courses in Arabic, Research Methods, and Statistics. Apart from teaching, I am also active in research activities individually and collaboratively and actively participate in conference activities and both as a presenter and participant. She can be contacted at email: ayudesrani@gmail.com.

Akhmad Shunhaji he is active as an academic as well as an educational practitioner. The main task is as a lecturer at the Postgraduate University of PTIQ Jakarta with additional assignments at this time, as Head of the Department of Islamic Education Management at the institution. Apart from that, Shunhaji is also chairman of the Al-Misbah Serpong Islamic Boarding School, teaching at STAI Fatahillah Serpong, PDU MUI North Jakarta, several Majelis Ta'lim in Jakarta. Other activities, as an Educational Consultant at several schools and active as a consultant for the development of Indonesian children's behavior. Last formal education, Al-Qur’an Science, and Interpretation Concentration of Al-Qur’an Based Education. In addition, he also completed non-formal education at the Indonesian Hypnotist Association (IHA), starting with certified hypnosis, certified hypnotherapist, and certified instructor. He can be contacted at email: akhmadshunhaji@ptiq.ac.id.

Ahmadi he is an active lecturer at the State Islamic Institute Ponorogo, Indonesia. He graduated from doctoral level in 2012 from the Department of Education Science/Education Management at the Nusantara Islamic University, Bandung. He is a productive lecturer in the field of scientific publications as part of his obligations in developing science on the campus where he serves. Apart from teaching, he is also actively involved in research activities and community service. Currently, he has served as Chair of the Institute for Research and Community Service since 2021. This has also made him active as a speaker at national and international scientific forums. He can be contacted at email: ahmadi@iainponorogo.ac.id.